

Residential Conditions of 'Hill Korwa' Primitive Tribe in North-Eastern Chhattisgarh: A Geographical Study

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Abstract:- Residential conditions have an important place in determining the family environment of a region. Housing is an indicator of the socio-economic status of the family. Therefore, residential status is an important unit of determining the quality of life of any population. The research paper presented is entirely on primary data. Raigarh, Jashpur, Surguja and Balrampur districts are located in the north-eastern region of the state of Chhattisgarh and in these areas there is majority of Hill Korwa primitive tribes. The total population of 1218 Hill Korwa families is 4701 in the Hill Korwa tribe families of the study area, in which 52.03 percent is male and 47.97 percent is female population of the total surveyed Hill Korwa tribe families of the study area, the highest number of 93.84 percent families have kutcha houses. It is clear from the analysis of the study area that in the surveyed village Kamarima (Jashpur district) of the state has got more than >30.01 positive housing index was obtained. Village Kamarima is a part of Jashpur Pat region, which has got more literate and educated population as compared to other surveyed areas and concentration of most educational centers is also visible in this village and it is necessary that an analytical study of the currently available residential facilities should be done. Accordingly on the basis of the analyzed study, a detailed planning outline should be prepared for the development of the area.

Keyword: *Type of House, Number of Rooms, Electrical System, Source of Drinking Water and Residential Status.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Residential conditions refer to the physical structure to which a person applies. In this structure, all the necessary services, facilities, equipment and devices of the environment are available, in which the family can develop and be nurtured physically, mentally and socially. The residential status of a family depends on their economic status and standard of living. Living conditions to human life has affects widely. Therefore, housing has an important place in human life and housing is one of the basic needs of human beings. Housing, apart from being a refuge for human beings, is also a place for mental peace and removal of physical fatigue.

In ancient times, due to being very backward, the Hill Korwa primitive tribe used to lead a nomadic life and even at present, they can be seen in the form of small settlements or hamlets at some places. Due to the low economic status of Hill Korwa primitive tribe, they are not able to build comfortable houses and build houses using local resources like grass, wood, clay etc, which has a direct impact is given on the standard of living of the families. In fact, the residence of Hill Korwa families presents the best example of human-nature interaction.

➤ Objective:

- To assess the residential conditions of the Hill Korwa primitive tribe of the study area.
- To calculate drinking water availability in Hill Korwa primitive tribe families.
- To Present planning for redressal of various residential problems in primitive tribes.

➤ Study Area:

Raigarh, Jashpur, Surguja and Balrampur districts in North-Eastern Chhattisgarh are situated between 24°30' to 21°00' north latitude and 82°30' to 84 30' east longitude. Its total geographical area is 23209.01 sq km. Is. According to the survey year 2005-06 in the study area, the total population of hill Korwa tribe is 28,164. Which is 0.11 percent of the population of the state and 0.36 percent of the total population of the tribes of the state and 1.2 percent of the total population of the north-eastern region. The northern region of the state, the plateau of eastern Baghelkhand and the Hill Korwa primitive tribe resides in the northern plateau and plateau region. The physical background of North-East Chhattisgarh has a clear impact on the cultural background. From the point of view of topography, the area is comprised of high land, plateau and plains, where the Western Chota Nagpur Plateau is extended. The highest peak in the study area is the Deogarh hills (Vindhya Range), which is 1370 meetar above sea level. Two drainage system in the state (Ganga and Mahanadi drainage system) has been found, which creates a tree-shaped drainage system similar to pulses.. The physical structure and relief of the area have a deep influence in its determination.

II. METHODOLOGY

The present study is mainly based on primary data. of North-Eastern Chhattisgarh for study Selection of total 20 villages from Hill Korwa dominated districts (Raigarh Jashpur Surguja and Balrampur) Study of residential conditions in 1218 Hill Korwa families through schedule by objective method Primary data is collected and analyzed on the basis of information. Study Basics Compilation of primary data through direct observation, interview and schedule from farmer families obtained through personal survey. For the measurement of the residential level of the surveyed villages of the state area of house according to residential conditions in Hill Korwa primitive tribe families Type Number of rooms, source of light, source of drinking water and number of available household items etc. On the basis of quality, their combined weighting index has been calculated by giving them separate weights. Firstly converting all these residential conditions into 'Z' score and measuring them as a separate unit classified as high, medium and low.

Fig 1 Location Map

➤ *Type of House*

Housing is the most basic need of human. The size and type of house reflects the habitability of human beings. Therefore, housing is a reflection of the social, economic status of a human being. On the basis of the materials from which the houses were constructed in the study area, the study has been done keeping the houses in two categories, semi-raw and raw. Out of the total surveyed Hill Korwa tribe families of the study area, 6.16 percent of the families have semi kutcha houses and maximum 93.84 percent of the families have kutcha houses. High percentage of families having semi kutcha house was found in Tedhasemar village (Raigarh district) of the surveyed area. Tedhasemar village is an area affected by Elephant menace, where Elephants cause loss of life and property, that is why the Hill Korwa families living here are forced to live sporadically at other places, due to which the abundance of semi-kutcha houses has been obtained. It is noteworthy that in the areas of the study area where the economic condition is strong, there is an abundance of kutcha houses, whereas where the economic condition is poor, there is an abundance of semi-kutcha houses.

➤ *Number Of Rooms*

The number of rooms has special importance in determining the residential condition of Hill Korwa. The economic and social status of a family can be measured on the basis of the number of rooms. The number of rooms where represents the size of the family. At the same time, it also reflects the economic condition of the family. The wealth and poverty of the family is known by the number of rooms. The Hill Korwa primitive tribe community did not have a permanent residence for a time, they used to lead a nomadic life. Gradually they got organized and started living as a tribe. Today he resides permanently. In this way, the influence of the periodical development of this tribe is visible in their residential condition today. The maximum number of rooms in the houses of 70.20 percent of the total surveyed families of Hill Korwa primitive tribe of the study area is one. On the contrary, houses with more than two rooms have been found to have the lowest percentage of 3.86 percent. In this way, the regional variation in the number of rooms in the houses of surveyed Hill Korwa families is the result of variation in their economic status.

➤ *Electrical System*

Electricity is an integral part of human habitation. Electricity is commonly used for lighting in the study area. The arrangement of electricity is minimal in the houses of the Hill Korwa primitive tribe community, that's why they arrange lighting in their houses by lighting a chimney, in which kerosene is used. The fire always keeps burning in the stove of their houses during cold or rainy days. Due to which light remains in that room of the total surveyed Hill Korwa families in the study area, 38.92 percent houses have electricity facilities. Maximum 61.08 percent families are still deprived of electricity facilities. Even today primitive means of lighting are being used by Hill Korwa families, in which chimney is used in maximum 44.66 percent of the houses, while the use of lantern was reflected in 16.42 percent of the families. In the study area, 100 percent houses

with electricity facilities were found in Amanara and Ganeshpur villages (Raigarh district). Electricity facility is available in the villages situated in the flat plains of the study area, but there is lack of electricity facility in the tolapara locality of the Hill Korwa settled in remote hilly and inaccessible areas. It is noteworthy that in the state of Chhattisgarh, the number of people living below the poverty line to provide 30 units of electricity free of cost to families with single light connections and 100 percent families of the surveyed Hill Korwa tribe are living below the poverty line. Still, the administration has not been able to provide the benefits of this scheme to these special backward tribal families. That's why even today the most surveyed Hill Korwa families are deprived of electricity.

➤ *Drinking Water Source*

The statement "Water is life" is true because oxygen is supplied to the human body only through water. Water is important in our daily life. In the study area, river/nala, well and handpump are the main sources of drinking water. Flat plains hand pump is the main source of drinking water in the villages living in the areas, but there are many Hill Korwa villages, where access is very difficult due to the hill and hilly areas, in such areas the main source of drinking water is river/nala and well/dodhi. River/Nala and well/Dhodhi is a self-flowing source mainly present in the hilly areas. Out of the total surveyed Hill Korwa households in the study area, 26.52 percent use river/nala as a source of drinking water, while 16.67 percent Hill Korwa Family well/Dhodhi and maximum percentage of Hill Korwa families use hand pump water.

➤ *Residential Status*

For the measurement of the residential level of the surveyed villages of the state, the area of the house, type of house, number of rooms, source of light, source of drinking water and number and quality of available household articles etc. By giving separate weights, their combined weighting index has been calculated. Firstly, all these residential conditions have been measured as separate units by converting them into "Z" score. It is noteworthy that all the economic conditions have difficulty in joint measurement for the common level of economic, therefore the combined index has been obtained by obtaining positive and negative values of different Z scores. It is also worth mentioning here. During the measurement, the residential level of the Hill Korwa primitive tribe is low. The figures of combined index mentioned in table number 1.1 were found to be positive and negative. Which are classified into high, medium and low level.

➤ *High Residential Index*

It is clear from the analysis of the study area that in the surveyed village Kamarima (Jashpur district) of the state, more than >30.01 positive housing index was obtained. The surveyed village-Kamarima is a part of Jashpur Pat region, which got more literate and educated population than other surveyed areas. At the same time, the concentration of most educational centers was also seen in this village. Due to the excess of pat and plateau area, the tendency of mustard and tau crop production has been found to be high, due to the

availability of irrigation facilities, there is an excess of bi-cropped area. Residential status of Hill Korwa primitive tribe families is assessed by their occupational structure. Therefore, with the increase in the high economic level in the village, an increase in their income has been found. It is clear that a clear direct positive relationship has been found between the residential level and economic level of the Hill Korwa primitive tribe.

➤ *Moderate Residential Index*

The surveyed village Ghatgaon (Balrampur district) of Samaripat area is included in the medium residential index. Collective index of this village ranges from 15.01 to 30.00 In terms of area of house, type of house, number of rooms,

source of light, source of drinking water and available household articles, this village maintains medium ratio, where most of the population is engaged in agriculture work, while only 183 percent population is employed in government service. is attached. 50.48 percent of the village is under uncropped area. At the same time, the forest area has been found to be relatively less, while the lack of arable land is visible. Education has an important place in the determination of the residential status in the Hill Korwa primitive tribe families of the surveyed village. there is an increase in the educational level, especially in the primary and secondary level, as a result of which the average residential level index is obtained.

Table 1 North-Eastern Chhattisgarh: Residential Index

S.N.	District	Name of Surveyed Villages	Residential level						
			House of Area	House of Type	No. of Rooms	Light of Source	Source of Drinking Water	Available Domestic Belongings	Composite Index
1	Raigarh	Amanara	-0.4	-0.43	-0.42	-2.52	-2.36	0.21	-6.34
		Ganeshpur	-1.31	-0.78	-1.32	-2.02	-1.84	-0.17	-7.44
		Tedhasemar	-1.72	-2.48	-1.78	-2.05	3.9	-1.1	-13.03
		Pusaudera	-1.65	-0.53	-1.66	-2.09	-1.23	-0.38	-7.54
		Chuhipahar	-1.79	-1.29	-1.81	-2.15	3.07	-0.8	-10.91
2	Jashpur	Larangapat	-1.04	-0.48	-1.05	-2.16	1.13	-0.51	-6.36
		Lodhenapat	-1.82	-0.82	-1.84	-1.59	2.97	-0.93	-9.97
		Chalni	-1.65	0.73	-1.53	-1.74	2.38	-0.72	-8.75
		Chhichhili 'A'	-1.51	-0.66	-1.56	-2.24	2.61	-1.1	-9.68
		Kamarima	11.1	4.08	10.94	7.51	6.92	3.03	43.54
3	Surguja	Lalmati	-0.97	-0.55	1.82	-0.64	-0.76	0.5	-5.24
		Bhediya	-1.78	-0.8	-1.79	0.94	-1.35	-0.46	-7.12
		Karra	-0.38	-0.34	-0.4	-1.69	-2.09	0.63	-5.53
		Rawai	-0.7	0.58	-1.01	-1.54	2.79	-0.8	-7.42
		Jori	-1.48	-0.71	-1.5	-1.18	-0.73	-1.05	-6.65
4	Balrampur	Lau	-0.59	-0.34	-0.6	-1	-0.52	0.42	-3.47
		Sewari	1	0.84	1.03	2.26	1.54	0.71	7.38
		Bantidarh	-1.4	-0.58	-1.32	-2.18	-1.84	0.63	-7.95
		Patrapara	1.94	0.79	1.89	3.13	-1.94	0.46	-10.15
		Ghatgaon	3.24	1.57	3.18	3.59	3.53	1.43	16.54

Source: Individual Count by Researcher, 2022

Table 2 North-Eastern Chhattisgarh: Residential Index

S.N	Residential Level	Residential Index	No. of Villages	Villages Name
1	High	> 30-01	1	Kamarima
2	Moderate	15-01&30	1	Ghatgaon
3	Low	< 15	18	Sewari, Lau, Lalmati, Karra, Amanara, Larangapath, Jori, Bhediya, Rawai, Ganeshpur, Pusaudera, Bantidarh Chalni, Chhichhli 'A', Lodhenapath, Patrapara, Tedhasemar and Chuhipahar

Source: Individual Count by Researcher, 2022

➤ *Low Residential Index:*

Eighteen villages are included under this in the area, out of which a total of seventeen (Sewari, Lau, Lalmati, Karra, Amanara, Larangapath, Jori, Bhediya, Rawai, Ganeshpur, Pusaudera, Bantidarh Chalni, Chhichhli 'A', Lodhenapath, Patrapara and Tedhasemar) villages in Jashpur-Samaripat and Raigad plateau area and one (Chuhipahar) village is situated in the hilly part of south-west Chhuri Udaipur. Due to the backwardness of all the above surveyed villages, their composite index was found to be less than 15. This area has a low standard from residential point of view. Most of the Hill Korwa primitive tribes of the surveyed villages are dependent on agriculturist jhuming agricultural land are still in a backward state. Due to excess of Pat and Plateau area, the production in agricultural land is less, as well as the Hill Korwa family is forced to live by collecting wages and forest produce. Lack of physical facilities was found in these areas and there is lack of awareness among the Hill Korwa families here due to their culture, whereas due to lack of road and other infrastructure, education has not been fully developed, which is low residential. This is the main reason for achieving the level index table no. 1.2.

III. CONCLUSION

Due to the low economic condition of Hill Korwa primitive tribe, they are not able to build comfortable houses, which directly affects the standard of living of the families. Hill Korwa primitive tribe families of the area have started living permanently and all the Hill Korwa families surveyed have their own house as a result of opportunity towards sustainable agriculture. Electricity facility is available in the villages situated in the same flat plains. Therefore, it is necessary that at present the appropriate benefits of the 'Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana' provided by the government are being given to the Hill Korwa primitive tribe family, it should be investigated by the responsible officers and told about the scheme. So that social awareness can be brought in them.

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